

Accelerating PWR Decommissioning by Shortening Spent-Fuel Cooling Time for Dry-Cask Storage

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on optimising the cooling time of Spent Nuclear Fuel (SNF) discharged from a Pressurised Water Reactor (PWR). The goal is to reduce the time SNF spends in the spent fuel pool (SFP) before being safely transferred to a dual-purpose dry storage cask (GBC-32). Feasibility was assessed by analysing the limiting factors: decay heat and the resultant dose rate equivalent (on the cask surface and at 2 m distance). The core modification involves replacing the peripheral layer of Fuel Assemblies (FAs) (16 storage positions, 50 % cask capacity) with rectangular prisms shielding dummies made of polyethylene, steel, or a combination thereof. The results show that replacing the peripheral layer of FAs with shielding fuel dummies significantly reduces the required cooling time compared with the standard loading pattern. From the shielding perspective, all dummy types-polyethene, steel, and combined-allow a reduction of approximately 9 years while keeping surface and 2 m dose rates within limits. However, decay heat remains the limiting factor, permitting only a 2.5 year reduction. Overall, the modification enables faster and safer transfer of SNF to dry storage. The results obtained apply to standard SNF management practices, particularly in the context of Nuclear Power Plant (NPP) decommissioning or other scenarios where minimising the residence time of fuel in the SFP is of critical importance.

Keywords: Decommissioning, Spent nuclear fuel, Fuel dummies, GBC-32 cask, PWR 17x17

1. INTRODUCTION

At the end of an NPP's operational life, decommissioning becomes a crucial step to ensure long-term safety, environmental protection, and potential future reuse of the site. There are three widely recognised strategic approaches to decommissioning: immediate dismantling, delayed dismantling, and entombment [1]. These models vary in terms of timing, cost, and regulatory requirements, but they all aim for the same outcome: the safe decontamination, dismantling, and disposal of NPP systems.

Before decommissioning can officially commence, the NPP must be defueled, meaning that all SNF is removed from the reactor and transferred to storage. This requirement is illustrated by the United Kingdom's policy, which states that ownership of the reactor is transferred to the Nuclear Decommissioning Authority only after complete defueling [2]. Therefore, defueling is the first significant milestone in the decommissioning process, both technically and financially.

Two primary storage methods are utilised worldwide: wet storage in pools and dry storage in casks. In recent decades, dry storage has become the preferred method due to its passive safety features, lower operating costs, and technical simplicity. This method typically costs between 100–200 \$ per kilogram of uranium [3]. However, before SNF can be transferred to dry storage, it must first be cooled in a SFP

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for a period of 1 to 10 years, depending on the cask design. Reducing this cooling time can accelerate decommissioning and minimise the duration that operators need to maintain ageing, actively cooled SFP systems.

Nevertheless, reducing the cooling time introduces several challenges. Higher decay heat and dose rate levels increase thermal and radioactive loads on the cask, complicating compliance with design and transport limits. Therefore, any reduction in cooling time requires a technically justified solution that ensures safety margins are maintained.

One promising approach to this challenge is the use of shielding fuel dummies, which can replace part of the SNF in the cask. While this solution reduces cask capacity and increases material requirements, it enables the use of existing licensed technologies without requiring new design certification. The application of this method to expedite SNF transfer represents a practical step toward achieving safer and more efficient decommissioning.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Fuel Dummies

The fuel dummies are non-fuel components designed as rectangular prisms that ideally fit within the fuel basket, occupying the peripheral layer. In this configuration, they provide additional shielding at the expense of occupying 16 positions (50 % cask capacity) that would otherwise be available for actual SNF. The materials chosen for the fuel dummies were selected based on their shielding capabilities. The steel dummy is made from Type 304 stainless steel, which has a density of 7.92 g/cm^3 , the same material used for the cask body. In contrast, the polyethylene dummy is composed of high-density polyethylene with a density of 0.95 g/cm^3 . Polyethylene, due to its high hydrogen content, effectively moderates and shields fast neutrons through absorption, as evidenced by its high neutron removal cross-section. Conversely, steel offers substantial attenuation of gamma radiation due to its high density and atomic number, resulting in a lower half-value layer.

Figure 1. Geometry of fuel dummies: polyethylene (left), steel (center), combined (right).

A combined fuel dummy was developed to reduce the dose rate equivalent. This dummy features a rectangular configuration, with an inner region composed of polyethylene (red) and an outer region consisting of steel (yellow) with a uniform wall thickness of 1 cm. The materials used for the combined dummy are identical to those employed for the individual polyethylene and steel dummies. This configuration reflects a more realistic engineering implementation, as it avoids potential phase-related or structural limitations associated with a standalone polyethylene dummy. Figure 1 illustrates the precise geometry of the fuel dummies.

2.2. Depletion, Decay and Source Calculations

The reference configuration of the PWR 17x17 FA comprises 264 fuel rods with a density corresponding to approximately 96 % of the theoretical maximum and an enrichment level of 4.5 wt% U-235 [4]. The

rods are positioned in a rectangular lattice arrangement, with uniform enrichment assumed throughout the entire FA. No burnable absorbers are included in the model, and the effect of control rods is neglected, since their presence has a negligible influence on the characteristics of high-burnup fuel. The gap between the fuel pellets and the zirconium cladding is filled with pressurised helium. Additionally, the FA features 24 guide tubes and a central instrument tube, all of which are fabricated from the same zirconium alloy as the cladding.

For the two-dimensional depletion analyses, the computational code SCALE [5] was employed, utilising the TRITON module in combination with the T-DEPL control sequence. The T-DEPL sequence performs multigroup deterministic transport simulations through the NEWT module and couples them with depletion calculations executed by ORIGEN. The nuclear data applied in these simulations were derived from the ENDF/B-VII.1 cross-section library [6] and processed into a 252-group neutron energy structure.

All fuel rods of the reference FA were assumed to deplete uniformly at a constant specific power of 60 MW/MTU [7] until reaching a burnup of 45 GWd/MTU [4], without accounting for reactor outages. The FA was modelled as an infinite lattice, representing a homogeneous reactor environment to eliminate boundary effects.

Figure 2. Relative neutron and gamma spectrum, 200n47g.

For shielding calculations, the isotopic composition and the corresponding neutron (200-group) and gamma (47-group) spectrum (see Figure 2) were evaluated after 10 years of cooling, which corresponds to the assumed cooling time for the reference FA [8]. Over this period, the relative spectral distributions remain nearly constant [9]. UO_2 , primarily O-16 and U-238, dominate the composition, while minor actinides and fission products contribute only marginally and have a limited influence on shielding results.

The MCNP 6.3.1 Monte Carlo code [10] was employed to perform criticality calculations and determine the effective multiplication factor k_{eff} , using the same model as described in 2.3. Although the evaluation of criticality was not the primary objective of this study, the calculated k_{eff} values were required to account for subcritical neutron multiplication in the determination of the neutron source strength. Based on these results, the neutron and gamma source strengths were subsequently determined using the ORIGEN computational code. Table I summarises the calculated k_{eff} values for the evaluated loading patterns used in the neutron source determination. The lowest k_{eff} corresponds to the configuration with combined fuel dummies.

Finally, all source strengths were normalised to be directly proportional to the number of FAs in the loading pattern and inversely proportional to the active fuel length of the cask model (normalised to 1 cm). The resulting values used in the shielding calculations are presented in Figure 3.

Table I. Comparison of the effective multiplication factor for different loading patterns.

Loading pattern	k_{eff} (-)
Standard loading pattern	0.2937
Polyethylene fuel dummies	0.2371
Steel fuel dummies	0.2629
Combined fuel dummies	0.2318

Figure 3. Gamma (left) and neutron (right) source strength of the cask.

2.3. Shielding Calculations

As illustrated in Figure 4, the GBC-32 cask [7], comprising 32 FAs in the standard loading pattern, was chosen to assess the feasibility of fuel dummies. This model is widely recognised as a benchmark configuration for burnup credit analyses. It is important to note that the GBC-32 does not represent a real, physical cask; instead, it is an idealised numerical standard developed at Oak Ridge National Laboratory.

The cask body is constructed from Type 304 stainless steel with a density of 7.92 g/cm^3 and features a radial wall thickness of 20.0 cm, an inner diameter of 175.0 cm, and an outer diameter of 215.0 cm. Between adjacent storage cells, Boral plates are made of an aluminium alloy matrix dispersed with boron carbide (B_4C). The total thickness of the Boral panels is 0.26 cm. Each storage cell has an inner width of 22.0 cm, a wall thickness of 0.75 cm, and a pitch of 23.5 cm. Inside the cask, the fuel basket is constructed from an aluminium alloy with a density of 2.70 g/cm^3 , providing structural support for the 32 PWR FAs. The internal cavity of the cask is filled with pressurised helium, and the cask is surrounded by dry air.

Figure 4. GBC-32 cask model with standard (left) and combined dummy (right) loading patterns.

Gamma radiation from activated end plugs and spacer grids was not included, as its contribution to the

total gamma source term is minor compared to that of the SNF. The nuclear data used for the shielding calculations were obtained from the ENDF/B-VII.1 cross-section library. Continuous-energy data were applied for all materials, and for polyethylene, the thermal scattering kernels $S(\alpha, \beta)$ was also included.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Azimuthal Distribution of Dose Rate Equivalent

Based on MCNP shielding calculations of the dose rate equivalent, the results were analysed for a ten-year cooling period of SNF, with all values normalised to the maximum value obtained with the standard loading pattern. For the standard loading pattern, the dose rate equivalent is overwhelmingly dominated by neutrons, accounting for more than 99 % of the total dose rate equivalent. Contributions from primary photons are negligible, whereas secondary photons generated by neutron interactions contribute only a tiny fraction, approximately 0.0025 %. The results shown in Figure 5 illustrate how the relative dose rate equivalent varies as a function of the azimuthal angle around the SNF cask.

Figure 5. Relative dose rate equivalent at the surface (left) and 2 m from the surface (right).

The reference value for the standard loading pattern was established to 1.0, which corresponds to the regulatory limit of 100 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$ measured at a distance of 2 m from the cask surface, as summarised in Table II. The analysis revealed that the most significant reduction in dose rate was achieved using polyethene fuel dummies, which lowered the relative dose rate to approximately 3.6 % of the standard configuration. Combined fuel dummies, made of both steel and polyethene, yielded similar results with a relative value of approximately 5.0 %. In contrast, steel-only dummies exhibited considerably higher dose rates, reaching nearly 38 % of the reference value.

These findings clearly indicate that implementing fuel dummies can substantially reduce the dose rate equivalent of SNF after ten years of cooling. This improvement results from both the decrease in the number of stored FAs and the addition of extra shielding materials. Therefore, the use of fuel dummies represents a practical and effective method for mitigating dose rates, enabling the optimisation of existing dry storage systems without significant structural modifications or costly redesigns.

Table II. Relative average dose rate equivalent compared to the standard loading pattern.

Loading pattern	Average relative dose rate equivalent (-)	
	Surface	2 m
Standard loading pattern	1.0000	1.0000
Polyethylene fuel dummies	0.0363	0.0361
Steel fuel dummies	0.3811	0.3830
Combined fuel dummies	0.0505	0.0503

3.2. Time-Dependent Behavior of Dose Rate Equivalent

Due to the two-dimensional approximation, the predicted dose rate equivalents are conservatively over-estimated by several tens of per cent compared with those obtained using a three-dimensional model [11]. This discrepancy arises from the reflective boundary conditions applied on the axial planes, which artificially limit neutron leakage in the axial direction. As a result, the effective neutron multiplication and source intensity increase, yielding higher dose rate equivalent values. Consequently, the 2D model produces conservative estimates relative to the more physically accurate 3D configuration. Given these considerations, all results were subsequently normalised to the standard loading pattern to ensure that, at approximately ten years of cooling, the transport limits for the dual-purpose cask are satisfied under the assumption of the reference configuration.

Figure 6 illustrates the time evolution of the dose rate equivalent as a function of the cooling time of SNF stored in the SFP for a specific loading pattern. The plotted data represent the maximum dose rate values observed in various azimuthal directions around the cask. The results show that all loading

Figure 6. Effect of cooling time on dose rate equivalent at the surface (left) and 2 m from the surface (right).

patterns incorporating fuel dummies satisfy the cask transport limits even at the minimum cooling time. During the first two years of cooling, steel fuel dummies provide the lowest dose rate values, after which the combined dummies become the most effective configuration. Polyethylene dummies exhibit slightly higher initial dose rates due to their lower gamma-shielding efficiency, but remain well below the legislative limit and show a steady decrease over time. Overall, the use of fuel dummies significantly shortens the required cooling period of SNF in the SFP while maintaining compliance with transport safety criteria. Despite reducing the cask capacity by 16 positions, this approach offers a practical and readily applicable solution based on existing, licensed technologies.

3.3. Time-Dependent Behavior of Decay Heat

The decay heat analysis, based on the model described in Section 3 and calculated using the ORIGEN module, focuses solely on radionuclide decay heat as a function of cooling time. The analysis does not incorporate modelling of gamma heating, the temperature field, or heat transfer within the cask. Since all dummy loading patterns contain the same number of FAs and dummies, the resulting decay heat values are identical; therefore, a single curve labelled “Fuel dummies” is shown in Figure 7. The GBC-32 cask does not have a defined design limit for decay heat; therefore, a reference limit of 32 kW was adopted from the CASTOR X/32 S cask, which is also a dual-purpose SNF cask with comparable enrichment and burnup characteristics [12]. Based on these assumptions, the standard loading pattern meets this limit after approximately 5.5 years of cooling, whereas the configurations with fuel dummies reach it after roughly 3 years.

Although the exact thermal design limit for the GBC-32 may differ from the assumed reference, the relative comparison clearly indicates that any realistic limit would still favour configurations employing fuel dummies. Thus, decay heat is identified as the primary parameter determining the required

cooling time. Considering both shielding performance and heat generation, the most practical design corresponds to a combined dummy configuration with a polyethylene core enclosed in a steel casing, ensuring mechanical integrity and containment even under extreme conditions.

Figure 7. Effect of cooling time on decay heat for different loading patterns.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrated that replacing a portion of SNF with shielding fuel dummies in the GBC-32 cask is a practical and viable approach for significantly reducing the required cooling time of SNF prior to dry storage. Based on comprehensive analyses (MCNP for dose rate equivalent and ORIGEN for decay heat), all proposed dummy configurations met the applicable regulatory limits, even at significantly shorter cooling periods compared to the standard loading pattern.

The results indicate a drastic improvement in radiation shielding: after ten years of cooling, polyethylene and combined dummies reduced the average azimuthal dose rate to approximately 3–5 % of the reference configuration, while the steel variant achieved about 38 %. From the shielding perspective, the use of fuel dummies represents a reduction of approximately 9 years in the required cooling time, as the dose rate equivalent at 2 m, which is the limiting parameter for transport safety, remains within regulatory limits. Despite this success in shielding, the required cooling time can only be shortened from roughly 5.5 to 3 years from the perspective of decay heat, confirming that decay heat remains the principal limiting factor of the modification.

Crucially, this approach uses existing, licensed technologies, eliminating the need for new cask development or costly certification. Although reducing 16 FA positions lowers overall cask capacity and economic efficiency, the proposed approach is not intended as an economically optimal transport solution. Rather, it provides a rapid and effective method for SNF removal in situations requiring accelerated reactor defuelling, such as during decommissioning, where timely achievement of key project milestones outweighs transport efficiency considerations.

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